

Photometric dimensions and radiation dimensions

Harald Schröer

2015

We compare the radiation dimensions (see table):

physical radiation dimension	unit	photometric radiation dimension	unit
radiant flux or radiant power Φ_e	Watt = W	luminous flux Φ_v	Lumen = lm
radiant intensity I_e	$\frac{W}{sr}$	luminous intensity I_v	Candela =cd
irradiance E_e	$\frac{W}{m^2}$	illumination or illuminance E_v	$\frac{lm}{m^2}$ =Lux
radiance or radiance L_e	$\frac{W}{m^2sr}$	luminance L_v	$\frac{cd}{m^2}$
surface radiant intensity density w_e	$\frac{W}{m^2sr}$	surface luminous intensity density w_v	$\frac{cd}{m^2}$
line radiant intensity density $\bar{w}_e$	$\frac{W}{m \cdot sr}$	line luminous intensity density $\bar{w}_v$	$\frac{cd}{m}$

The physical radiation dimensions are often written with the index e (energy) and the photometric dimensions with the index v (visual). The photometric radiation dimensions are named as physiological radiation dimensions, also.

To physical radiation dimensions analogous equations are valid as to photometric radiation dimensions.

With the help of the physical radiation field dimensions the derivations of equations are the same as at the photometric dimensions. These equations are valid only for the visual wavelengths area.

The relation between a photometric dimension X_v and the belonging physical

radiation dimension X_e is:

$$X_\nu = K_m \cdot \int_0^\infty X_{\lambda,e} \cdot V_\lambda d\lambda$$

see Hammer [2] chapter 7.4.3.1 p.179 with $\lambda =$ wavelength

$$K_m = 6.8 \cdot 10^2 \text{lm watt}^{-1}$$

and to spectral radiant flux:

$$\Phi_{\lambda,e} = \frac{d\Phi_e}{d\lambda}$$

Figure to V_λ :

V_λ is the spectral luminosity sensitivity. For $\lambda = 555 \text{ nm}$ V_λ has the maximum value 1. The area with $V_\lambda > 0$ extends from 380 nm to 790 nm, this is the visual wavelengths area. V_λ is a strictly increasing function in the interval (380 nm, 555 nm) and a strictly decreasing function in the interval (555 nm, 790 nm) to λ (see figure).

Further information can be found in Hammer [2] chapter 7.4 p.172-181 and Kuchling [1] chapter 27 p.380-392. In these two books there are tables of V_λ , too. At $\lambda = 430 \text{ nm}$ and 480 nm the values for V_λ in Hammer [2] or Kuchling [1] are incorrect.

To surface radiant intensity density respectively to line radiant intensity density we have the following equations.
source with surface $B(t)$:

$$\int_{B(t)} w_e(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} = I_e \quad \vec{b} \in B(t)$$

line source with form $L(t)$:

$$\int_{L(t)} \bar{w}_e(\vec{b}, t) d\vec{b} = I_e \quad \vec{b} \in L(t)$$

The parametrization of (2) from chapter 7 (see Schröder [3]) can be used for both formulas.

Though radiance and surface radiant intensity density respectively luminance and surface luminous intensity density have the same units, they are in general different dimensions, see Hammer [2] chapter 7.4.1.4 p.173.

References

- [1] Horst Kuchling "Taschenbuch der Physik" 1979 Verlag Harri Deutsch Frankfurt on the Main
- [2] Karl Hammer "Grundkurs der Physik Teil 2" 3.edition Oldenbourg Verlag Munich 1987
- [3] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Verlag Wissenschaft & Technik Berlin 2001